

CE25006 – ROV Monitoring Survey

CE25006 ROV
Monitoring Survey

RV Celtic Explorer and Holland 1 ROV - Cruise Number CE25006

Galway - South Coast Cork - Belgica Mound Province - Galway

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Aaron Lim ^{1, 2)}*, Larissa de Oliveira ^{1, 2)}, Corie Boolukos ^{1, 2)}, Ruaihri Strachan ³⁾, Dominic Bush ^{1, 2)}, Gerard Summers ^{1, 2)}, Kevin Walsh ^{1, 2)}, Cara Brennan ^{1, 2)}, Luca Caminiti ^{1, 2)}, Irene Loriga ^{1, 2)}, Bonnie Young ^{1, 2)}, Julian O Malley ^{1, 4)}, *Holland 1* ROV technical team, Officers and Crew of the RV Celtic Explorer

- 1) *Department of Geography, University College Cork, Ireland*
- 2) *Environmental Research Institute, University College Cork, Ireland*
- 3) *Green Rebel Ltd, Cork, Ireland*
- 4) *School of Biological, Earth and Environmental Sciences, Cork, Ireland*

Corresponding author*: aaron.lim@ucc.ie

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Executive Summary

This remotely operated vehicle (ROV) monitoring survey aimed to acquire data onboard RV Celtic Explorer with the *Holland 1* ROV from April 24th 2025 to May 4th 2025 in support of UCC-led scientific research projects. These projects include assessment of shipwreck-derived pollution, cold water coral (CWC) reef spatio-temporal variation and mound development. As such, a geophysical array consisting of a Geomatrix G882 Magnetometer and Edgetech 4205 side scan sonar (SSS) was used simultaneously with a hull-mounted Kongsberg EM2040 to map various potentially polluting wrecks and CWC reefs. Downward and oblique-facing ROV video footage were subsequently acquired across the mapped wrecks and reefs with tight line spacing to ensure full coverage imagery for photogrammetric reconstruction (60% overlap required). All equipment (ROV, MBES, Geophysical array) were wet tested prior to commencement of survey operations. Mobilisation took place in Galway harbour from the 21st to 24th April and with wet testing taking place at Rossaveel on the 25th Of April. Geophysical, Hydrographic and ROV surveys of U58, SS Miami and HMS Alyssum were conducted from the 26th to 29th of April. ROV video inspection of the Piddington Mound (Belgica Mound Province) and surrounds were conducted from the 29th of April to 1st of May.

The geophysical and ROV surveys of each of the three wrecks yielded fruitful results from both an archaeological perspective, and more specifically, the standpoint of potential pollution. For U-58, the data indicated that many of the vessel's external structures, including the majority of its reserve fuel tanks, are either missing or severely damaged, in part due to trawling. Considerable amounts of unexploded Ordnance (UXO) were observed on the wreck. As it pertains to HMS Alyssum, the project succeeded in providing the first ever definitive confirmation of the wreck's identity, while also enabling a detailed investigation into site layout and transformation. Finally, visual data collected at the wreck of SS Miami offered further contextualization for previous remote-sensing surveys, namely, the sheer level of disarticulation that has occurred.

ROV-video data were systematically acquired across the entire surface of three CWC mounds to construct 3D structure-from-motion photogrammetric models of each. Two of these mounds were imaged by ROV-mounted bathymetry in 2015 but were never ground-truthed. On this survey, they were fully and systematically mosaicked for the first time and will be referred to as Lucy and Mila mounds (Lucy, the mound, due east-southeast of the Piddington Mound and Mila, the mound, to the southwest of Piddington Mound). The video-data acquired across the surface of Piddington Mound will contribute to a valuable temporal dataset. Imagery of Lucy and Mila mounds will test the validity of single mound observations and ecological succession of mounds at various stages for the first time. Although these three mounds are in close proximity, preliminary review of these video-data indicate that their biological composition varies considerably.

All data are stored on 3 Hard Drives (2 x UCC; 1 x MI ROV data only). Data will be used for on-going research projects at the Earth and Ocean Lab at UCC with collaborators.

Survey Background

Instability and Pollution Potential Mapping of Irish Shipwreck Sites for a National Risk Assessment Database (I-POINT)

Shipwrecks are anthropogenically derived seafloor features with important cultural heritage that may form biodiversity ‘hotspots’ in otherwise barren parts of the seabed. In recent times, their presence has typically been considered a hazard to trade and navigation (shipping routes), energy (renewable energy development) and marine resources (trawling). However, a relatively lesser studied hazard are potentially polluting wrecks (PPW) given their composition, fuel content, cargo and long-term exposure to the marine environment that can leak into the marine environment. The IPOINT project is a multi-disciplinary, multi-institutional research project that: i) identifies, maps and ranks the distribution of polluting shipwrecks around Ireland, and; ii) quantifies the impacts of the most intensely polluting wrecks. Detailed ROV investigation, geophysical data and 3D photogrammetry are key project deliverables that are also used in modelling the pathway of pollutants into the marine environment. The wrecks subject to investigation on this survey are the HMS Alyssum, SS Miami and U58.

a) SM U-58: Construction and History

SM U-58 was an ocean-going torpedo attack submarine, launched on 31 May 1916 at the A.G. Weser Shipyard in Bremen. It is one of twelve Type U-57 vessels built by the German Imperial Navy during World War I. U-58, as with most larger submarines, featured a steel double hull construction, made up of a stronger pressure hull that measured 54.2 m in length and a beam of 4.1 m, enveloped by an outer hull (length: 67 m, beam: 6.3 m) that gave the vessel its shape. The submarine had an overall height of 8.1 m (3.8 m draught) and a displacement of 956 tons when submerged. Two diesel engines (1,800 horsepower when surfaced) connected to two screw shafts and fed by two oil-ready tanks (621 litres each) propelled U-58 at speeds up to 14.7 knots. When fully-submerged, the submarine relied on a series of batteries to power the electric motors. The vessel carried up to 87 tons of oil in its external fuel tanks, which were situated in the cavities between the outer and pressure hulls. U-58 had space for a maximum crew of 40 men and 7 torpedoes, which were fired from torpedo tubes (0.5 m diameter) at the bow and stern. Additional armaments were located on the vessel’s surface deck, consisting of a 10.5 cm SK L/45 forward gun and an 8.8 cm SK L/30 aft gun.

U-58 began its career upon its commissioning on 9 August 1916 as a member of the II Flotilla. From October 1916 – November 1917, it sank 21 Allied ships, totalling 30,906 in gross register tonnage. On 17 November 1917, the American destroyer USS Fanning, while patrolling the waters off Cork Harbor, deployed a series of depth charges after making contact with a suspected submarine. The results of this action were inconclusive, though an oil slick was spotted on the sea surface. Eventually, the Fanning’s coxswain spotted a periscope, and shortly after, U-58 surfaced at a sharp, inclined angle. The depth charges had damaged the submarine’s hydroplanes and fuel lines, making it nearly impossible for U-58 to control its descent. After action reports indicated that the external injuries to the vessel appeared minimal. USS Fanning, joined by USS Nicholson, converged on the foundering submarine, shelling it until U-58’s occupants began to emerge in an apparent surrender. The German seamen were transferred aboard the American warships, while the submarine was held in place by mooring lines. Hopes of towing U-58 back to harbour were quickly dashed as the vessel began to list and then capsize, forcing the Fanning’s crew to cut the lines and allow the submarine to sink.

b) HMS *Alyssum* (British Minesweeper): Construction and History

HMS *Alyssum*, specially built in 1915 for the British war effort, is one of 44 Arabis-class sloops. Constructed at the Earle's Shipbuilding yard in Kingston upon Hull, the vessel measured 81.6 m in overall length and 10.2 m in beam, with a draught of 3.4 m. The 1250-ton *Alyssum* featured two decks laid flat (main and upper), as well as a raised forecastle deck and boat deck amidship. The steel-hulled ship was propelled by a three-cylinder triple expansion steam engine and two coal-fired, single-ended boilers. Coal bunkers were located both fore and aft of the boiler room, with two stacks amidship to help expel the exhaust smoke. The steel masts, fore and main, measured 23.7 m and 22.7 m, respectively. In addition to specialized minesweeping equipment and depth charges, *Alyssum's* armament included fore and aft QF 4.7-inch naval guns, and two QF 3-pounder (47 mm) Vickers flanking the rear gun. The vessel was manned by a crew of 90, including the captain and other officers.

Officially commissioned in December 1916, HMS *Alyssum* was originally based out of Yorkshire, England and assigned to the 10th Sloop Flotilla, which consisted of Arabis-class sloops. The vessel spent the first of year of service primarily engaged in minesweeping in the North Sea, supporting ships of Britain's Grand Fleet who sought to enter the German Bight. In February 1917, *Alyssum* and the remainder of the 10th Sloop Flotilla were transferred to Cobh, Ireland to be used as escort for Allied vessels crossing the Atlantic via the Western Approaches. A month later, on the 18th of March, *Alyssum* and fellow Arabis sloop, HMS *Myosotis*, were sweeping a minefield off County Cork's Galley Head. The mines, which had been laid by the German UC-66, sank another member of the 10th Sloop Flotilla, HMS *Mignonette*, the day prior. While executing these duties, *Alyssum* inadvertently detonated a mine, causing severe damage to the ship's hull. HMS *Myosotis* quickly took the disabled vessel under tow, as *Alyssum's* crew were safely transferred. Towing responsibilities were then assigned to a tugboat dispatched from Cork Harbor. Taking *Alyssum* by the stern, the tug headed back for the harbour, but water quickly started to fill the minesweeper. After an hour, the situation became untenable, and the towing lines were parted as *Alyssum* sank south of Incheydoney.

c) SS *Miami*: Construction and History

Steamship (SS) *Miami* was built by the Scottish shipbuilding firm, Barclay, Curle & Co., in 1904. The vessel measured 106.9 m in length, 14.1 m wide, and had a draught of 9.1 m. It featured four decks laid flat, in addition to raised forecastle, boat, and poop decks. The coal-burning steamship was powered by three-cylinder triple expansion engine and four single-ended boilers. The lower level of the hull was partitioned into four cargo holds, separated by the machinery rooms. Hold Two was used as a reserve bunker, where much of the ship's coal was stored. The vessel had a single stack amidship, and both a fore and aft mast. SS *Miami* was built specifically for the transportation of refrigerated cargo and featured two fan rooms above the shelter deck.

Upon the start of World War I, SS *Miami* was conscripted into service as an armed merchant ship, responsible for ferrying cargo across the Atlantic. On the 22nd of June 1917, the vessel passed Fastnet, Ireland on its way to Manchester, England, when it was sighted by the German submarine, UC-51. The U-Boat had been patrolling the waters off County Cork, having sunk the British steamships *Violet* and *Kangaroo* only four days earlier. SS *Miami*, which had departed New York City with a load of general cargo, including an estimated half a million bananas, was unaware of the impending threat. UC-51 fired a torpedo, which struck the steamship below the waterline. As the vessel began to sink, the crew of around 60 and passengers, abandoned the ship via lifeboats, while the captain radioed for assistance. All aboard were rescued by a naval escort ship that had reported to the scene soon shortly after the attack. While no lives were lost, SS *Miami* and its cargo sank south of Ballymacrown.

Cold water coral reef monitoring and reef development

Through a combination of biological growth of CWCs, local hydrodynamic regime and the resulting frictional drag of the coral framework, CWCs can trap current-suspended sediments to create topographic features on the seafloor called CWC mounds. CWC Mounds can range in height from 3 to 30 m in height (e.g. the Darwin Mounds) (Wheeler et al., 2008) and, through successive periods of mound development they can grow to >100 m in height (e.g. the Challenger Mound) (Kano et al., 2010). CWC mounds support biodiversity in deep sea ecosystems, providing habitats, breeding grounds and food for numerous species. They act as natural feeding grounds for commercially-sensitive fish and given their sediment trapping capability they can be used as detailed paleoenvironmental archives. However, given their dependence on allogenic environmental conditions such as current speeds, food availability and sediment supply, they are sensitive to environmental change. Although CWC reefs offshore Ireland have been growing for the past 2.6 Ma (Kano et al., 2009), recent research has shown that CWC mound surfaces can vary significantly over short timescales (Lim et al., 2018, Huvenne et al., 2016). Boolukos et al. (2019) show that over 4 years, one particular species of coral was in significant decline across one mound. Spatially, CWC mounds exhibit a range of surface features including dense live coral framework, dead coral framework, coral rubble, biogenic hash, sand and dropstones and hemipelagic sediment (de Oliveira et al., 2021). The quantity and distribution of features vary depending on exposure to the local hydrodynamic regime, food availability and sediment supply.

This survey maps and assesses the Moira Mound chain of CWC reefs located within the Belgica Mound Province (BMP) Special Area of Conservation (Porcupine Seabight). Within the BMP, giant cold water coral carbonate mounds exist in 2 broadly north to south parallel lines. Between them, there are over 300 small size cold water coral reefs called the Moira Mounds (Wheeler et al., 2011). There are three broad types: very small, isolated mounds ~3 m in height, mounds with scour 8 to 10 m in height and larger mounds with well-developed scour and coral ridges (Lim et al., 2018b). One of the large mounds with scour and coral ridges, named the Piddington Mound, has been the subject of detailed mapping and exhibits considerable sediment facies variation in both space and time (Lim et al., 2017).

Data from this survey feeds into on-going research on the small-sized CWC mounds whose aims broadly seek to understand mound variability in both space and time. The data will be processed at UCC using SonarWiz (backscatter), Qimera (bathymetry), OpenMag (magnetometry), Agisoft Metashape (photogrammetry), ArcPro, QGIS and Python (geospatial and spatial analyses).

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Survey Objectives

Fig. 1 Map showing main cruise track

The research survey has 7 scientific objectives:

1. Image the structure and reflectance of 3 potentially polluting shipwrecks along the south coast of Ireland via Side Scan Sonar (SSS), Magnetometry, and Multibeam Echosounder (MBES);
2. To quantify sediment type, ferrous objects such as unexploded Ordnance (UXO), habitats, and debris from shipwrecks to determine the characteristics of wreck-derived pollution based on analysis of acquired data;
3. To generate centimetre-scale 3D models of the HMS Alyssum, U58 and SS Miami wrecks for post-survey structural assessments and use in computation fluid dynamics simulations that determine their degradation, local seafloor erosion and pollutant transport pathways;
4. To determine the concentration and distribution of wreck-derived pollutants in wreck-proximal sediments;
5. To determine the relationship between cold-water coral mound distribution and dropstones through remotely-sensed geophysical data acquisition and post-survey assessment;
6. Geomorphologically characterise the Macnas Mound cold-water coral reefs and determine the proportion and distribution of coral framework across their surfaces and;
7. Determine if there is a spatial gradation/organisation at both a mound- and mound-chain scale at the Piddington Mound cold water coral mound, and surrounding mounds;

Equipment

RV Celtic Explorer

The RV Celtic Explorer is a 65.5 m multipurpose research vessel with a displacement of 2,425 tonnes operated by the Marine Institute of Ireland. The vessel has a dynamic positioning system (DP1), enabling station-keeping capabilities during precise sampling operations. It accommodates up to 31 personnel (15-17 scientists plus crew) an endurance up to 35 days with a cruising speed of 10 knots and maximum speed of 15 knots. The vessel is equipped with a 5×5 m moon pool, wet and dry laboratories totalling 180 m². Its acoustic suite includes hull-mounted MBES systems (ranging from 30 kHz, and 400 kHz), a Knudson sub-bottom profiler, and fisheries echosounders. For sampling operations, the vessel deploys equipment via a main A-frame with 25-tonne capacity and hydrographic winches capable of operating to depths of 6000 meters. The Explorer is classified as Ice Class 1D, permitting limited operations in ice-covered waters, and maintains a working deck area of 445 m² for scientific equipment deployment.

Figure 2 RV Celtic Explorer

Holland 1 ROV

The *Holland 1* ROV is a work-class remotely operated vehicle (ROV) capable of operations to 3000 m water depth. The system has dimensions of 3.2 × 1.9 × 2.1 m with a weight of 4500 kg in air. It utilises a 400 Hz hydraulic system with 150 hp and operates via a neutrally buoyant tether with fiber optic telemetry supporting HD video transmission. The ROV features two 7-function Kraft Predator manipulator arms with a maximum payload capacity of 100 kg. Sensor packages include a conductivity, temperature, depth (CTD) sensor and a suite of HD cameras including pan-and-tilt units. Navigation systems comprise a Doppler velocity log, ultra-short baseline (USBL) acoustic positioning system, altimeter, and depth sensor with precision to ±0.1 m. Inertial Navigation is achieved through ROVINS

Inertial Navigation System (INS) by IXBLUE. The vehicle is deployed via a dedicated launch and recovery system and requires a minimum operational team of 6 personnel for 24-hour operations.

Figure 3 Holland 1 ROV on deck prior to deployment with the aft USBL beacon (aft-starboard view)

Figure 4 Holland 1 ROV during deployment for downward-facing video deployment

Edgetech 4205 Side Scan Sonar (300/600 kHz)

The EdgeTech 4205 side scan sonar (SSS) is a dual-frequency SSS that operates at 300 kHz and 600 kHz. The system provides high-resolution imaging capabilities with maximum range coverage of approx. 300 m at 300 kHz and 100 m at 600 kHz. It is depth rated to 2000 m and can achieve a horizontal beam width of 0.5° at 600 kHz and 0.9° at 300 kHz, with along-track resolution of 1.5 cm at 600 kHz and 3 cm at 300 kHz. The towfish weighs approximately 23 kg in air and includes integrated pitch, roll, heading, depth and altimeter sensors for positional control and quality control (QC) during online surveying.

Figure 5 Edgetech 4205 Side Scan Sonar equipped with depressor wing, USBL beacon and Magnetometer in train (referred to as the Geophysical Array)

Figure 6 Image showing the Geophysical Array set up in 'piggyback' configuration

Geomatrix G882 Magnetometer

The Geomatrix G882 is a cesium vapor magnetometer for high-sensitivity magnetic anomaly detection. It has a sensitivity of <math><0.004\text{ nT}</math> with an absolute accuracy of 0.1 nT and a sampling range from 20,000 to 100,000 nT. The system operates at depths up to 4000 m and can achieve a sample rate of up to 20 Hz. The magnetometer weighs 44 kg in air (14 kg in water) and includes an integrated depth sensor and altimeter.

Kongsberg EM2040 Multibeam Echosounder

The Kongsberg EM2040 is a high-resolution MBES that can operate at 200 kHz, 300 kHz and 400 kHz in single, dual, or triple sectors with up to 800 soundings per ping. It can achieve a maximum ping rate of 50 Hz with swath coverage up to 5.5 times water depth, reaching a maximum of 85 degrees from nadir. Its depth range extends from less than 1 m to approximately 500 m (at 200 kHz) with a depth resolution of 1 cm. The sounder is integrated with a sound velocity probe at the hull of the vessel, Seapath MRU and C-Nav GNSS.

Figure 7 Kongsberg EM2040 Multibeam Echosounder

Methodology

Task 1.1 Vessel and ROV mobilisation, wet test and survey calibration

Datasets: EM2040 patch test lines

The vessel was mobilised for integration with the *Holland 1* ROV. Specifically this included set-up of the Dry Laboratory whereby: the ROV video streams will be displayed and saved to a series of HD's (saved to three separate places); a digital suite of data logs were set up; a central Geographic Information System (GIS) were created for use by shift leaders; EM302 and EM2040 were set up via SIS with survey lines uploaded; SSS and Magnetometer log files were created via QINSy; all ROV flight paths were uploaded and; all scientific IT work spaces were prepared. The wet laboratory was also set up for processing of all Day grab samples. This included all consumables (bags, markers, waterproof tape), labelling refrigerated spaces and safe storage of chemicals. The ROV laboratory computers were set up (for scientific party) to include digital log sheets for observations as well as HD camera stills,

background maps for the ROV team to plot flight track on and clear set of prioritised survey objectives. The Mobilisation period included a wet test of the ROV at Rossaveel.

The EM2040 patch test was carried out at HMS Alyssum following the line plan outlined in Figure 8. The lines were suitable for pitch, roll, latency and heading. The patch testing was carried out in post processing via QPS Qimera.

Figure 8 Line plan acquired with the EM2040 at HMS Alyssum for patch testing

Task 1.2 SSS Mobilisation, Interfacing and Verification

The side scan sonar was required to be towed behind the vessel during the survey using a MaCartney CORMAC Q3 winch. The EdgeTech 4205 MPMT towfish was fitted with a depressor wing in order to reduce the amount of cable out used whilst towing. A wireless cable counter located on a suspended sheave block (lifted onto the A-frame) is used to monitor the length of cable paid in and out during towing. The position for this towfish is provided from a USBL transponder beacon mounted on the tow assembly (jubilee clipped to the cable slightly above ahead of the towpoint). An offset was calculated from the beacon to the towfish centre of gravity (CoG).

SSS System	EdgeTech 4205 (SN: 63880) Depressor Wing (SN: 67348)
Operation and Frequency	Mode: Multi Pulse/ Motion Tolerant Low Frequency 230 kHz and High Frequency: 550 kHz
TPU	Edgetech Starmux IV (SN: 64358)
Operational Parameters	Control GUI: Discover 4205 MPMT Dual Frequency (V 44.0.1.1010) Towing: MaCartney CORMAC Q3 stainless steel winch with block/cable counter Position: derived through USBL transponder

Table 1: Sidescan sonar system to be used from RV Celtic Explorer.

The SSS towfish was verified by triggering both the LF and HF channels on deck temporarily and conducting a rub test on each transceiver, confirming that data was being received to the recording interface. This test was done in a starboard-port-starboard sequence. During these alongside tests,

auxiliary navigation was also configured to and from the SSS in the navigation software (based on a simulated position) and verified through the acquisition software.

Figure 9 Deck rub test for SSS towfish, with navigational data configured in the acquisition software.

Task 1.3 Magnetometer Mobilisation, Interfacing and Verification

A magnetometer was also required as part of the survey. For this, a Geometrics G-882 cesium vapor magnetometer (with digital board) was configured in tandem behind the SSS towfish, using a 10 m kevlar soft tow cable. This tows the magnetometer at a slightly lower altitude from the seabed to the SSS towfish (approximately 2 m lower), which reduces the true horizontal layback. The data is transmitted from the magnetometer through an onboard optional sensor port (RS-232) and outputted from the SSS acquisition software to the online navigation software (QINSy), where a dedicated magnetometer could be recorded. Position for the G-882 sensor itself was calculated based on a

variable node offset located aft of the SSS (9.9 m as measured) whilst under tow (based on the acquired transponder beacon position).

Magnetometer	Depth Sensor	Altimeter	Control and Acquisition
G-882 Digital (884108)	SN: 2024F028 Scale: 1 Bias: 0	SN: 13132.402984 Scale: 1 Bias: 0	Discover 4205 MPMT Dual Frequency (V 44.0.1.1010) QPS QINSy (V 9.7.6)

Table 2: Magnetometer equipment.

The magnetometer was verified whilst alongside by lowering the G-882 device over the stern using two lines with a small weight on the tail (in order to balance the device evenly through the water). The magnetometer was then raised at 1 m intervals to check that observations were consistent for depth and altitude measurements from the onboard altimeter and pressure sensor (located in the nose of the device). An anomaly check was also conducted whilst the device was in the water, by lowering a large shackle proximal to the sensor.

Figure 10 Alongside depth and altitude verification for G-882 magnetometer.

Figure 12 Alongside anomaly verification for G-882 magnetometer.

Task 2.1 Hydrographic and Geophysical Survey of wrecks

Datasets: Multibeam and backscatter grids x 3; Total Field and Residual Field Magnetometry grids x 3; SSS mosaics x 3

The Magnetometer was deployed 'piggybacked' from the Edgetech 4205 SSS at each of the 3 wreck sites. This is a standard geophysical array and ensures that the signal from the magnetometer is not impacted by the presence of the SSS. The SSS was towed approx. 7.5 m from the bottom with the magnetometer at approx. 5.5 m off the bottom. Survey lines were alongside each wreck (approx. 35 m port and starboard of each wreck) to ensure ensonification in the optimal side scan range. Each grid consisted of approx. 3 survey lines. Survey speed was at 4 knots. Simultaneously, the EM2040 acquired data at a frequency of 400 kHz and opening angles of only 65 degrees port and starboard of nadir. All acquisition was managed via Edgetech Discovery (SSS), Qinsy (Magnetometer) and SIS (EM2040). Some initial data processing took place during the survey to inform day grabs and ROV-dives as part of an embedded mitigation strategy.

Task 3.1 ROV-borne Photogrammetric survey of wrecks

Datasets: Suite of video footage across 3 wrecks; 3D models of 3 wrecks

The ROV was deployed at each of the 3 wrecks sites. A forward-facing HD camera was mounted on the front of the ROV. Positioning and navigation for the ROV during dives were achieved using a Sonardyne Ranger 2 USBL corrected by DVL and an IXSea INS (ROVINS). The ROV altimeter recorded and log the height of the ROV (and therefore camera) above the seabed. Forward-facing HD video were recorded during a series of transects covering the entire surface of each wreck. The flight path was uploaded to Global Mapper and Qinsy where the ROV team could follow the flight plan in real time plotted over previously acquired bathymetric data (INFOMAR). To maintain a clear image of the wreck surface, the ROV was flown <2 m from the wreck surface at a survey speed of <0.3 knots. Several lights were attached to the ROV to achieve homogenous lighting across the camera field of view. All

positioning data and video data were stored as text files and .mov files, respectively. With Agisoft Metashape, 3D models of each survey area were generated using structure-from-motion photogrammetry (Price et al., 2019; Lim et al., 2020).

Task 3.2 Day grabs

Datasets: physical sediment samples for pollution assessment at 3 x wreck sites

The day grab was deployed from the starboard side winch at 3 locations around each wreck (port, starboard and distal as control). The number and location of the target sampling sites were based on the lower frequency channel of the SSS mosaic, bathymetry and backscatter (EM2040). The mosaic were used to outline sediment variation. Each retrieved sample was stored in a large 10L plastic sampling bag which was labelled, bagged within an airtight sampling pocket and stored within the refrigerated space in the wet lab.

Task 4.1 Hydrographic and Geophysical Survey of the Macnas and Moira Mounds

Datasets: backscatter grid; high-density sounding grid; Total Field and Residual Field Magnetometry grid; SSS mosaic

The Magnetometer was deployed 'piggybacked' from the Edgetech 4205 SSS (hereby referred as geophysical array). The survey started in shallower water near the Macnas Mounds with the geophysical array towed perpendicular to the depth contours down the shelf (Eastern Porcupine Seabight) across the upslope, midslope and downslope Moira Mound site. The aim of this transect is to image the mounds via various sensors and to ascertain at which depth the geophysical array would be able to fish given constraints on cable out (~800 m on the winch). The geophysical array was towed in this case at steerage (~3 knots). This, plus both early deployment and the depressor wing, helped the array to fish at <10m off the bottom in places. Simultaneously, the EM2040 acquired data at a frequency of 200 kHz with opening angles of only 65 degrees port and starboard of nadir. All acquisition was managed via Edgetech Discovery (SSS), Qinsy (Magnetometer) and SIS (EM2040). Some initial data processing took place during the survey.

Task 5.1 ROV-borne Photogrammetric survey of reefs

Datasets: Suite of video footage across 4 reefs; 3D models of 4 reefs

The ROV was deployed at 4 reefs at different locations within the downslope Moira Mound area. A downward-facing HD camera was mounted on the bottom of the ROV. Positioning and navigation for the ROV during dives were achieved using a Sonardyne Ranger 2 USBL (ultra-short baseline positioning system) corrected by an IXSea INS. The ROV altimeter recorded and logged the height of the ROV (and therefore camera) above the seabed. Downward-facing HD video were recorded during a series of transects covering the entire surface of each reef using a boustrophedonic ROV-specific flight plan previously proposed by Lim et al. (2018). The flight path was uploaded to Global Mapper where the ROV team can follow the flight plan in real time plotted over previously acquired bathymetric data (CE19008: Symons_MoM). To maintain a clear image of the wreck surface, the ROV was flown <2 m from the reef surface at a survey speed of <0.4 knots. Several lights were attached to the ROV to achieve homogenous lighting across the camera field of view. A white balance calibration was performed at the start of each video survey. All positioning data will be stored as text files. With Agisoft Metashape, 3D models of each survey area will be generated using structure from motion (Price et al., 2019; Lim et al., 2020).

The ROV was deployed at the Piddington, Lucy and Mila Mounds. A downward-facing HD camera was mounted on the front of the ROV. Positioning and navigation for the ROV during dives were achieved using a Sonardyne Ranger 2 USBL (ultra-short baseline positioning system) corrected by DVL and an IXSea Inertial Navigation System (ROVINS). The ROV altimeter recorded and log the height of the ROV (and therefore camera) above the seabed. The initial part of this long dive was used as a large reconnaissance survey to ensure positional accuracy of previously-acquired ROV-mounted MBES bathymetry and therefore allowing the bathymetric dataset to be used as a basemap for mound-scale mosaicking. Once the layout of the map was verified by the ROV pilots and scientific party, the co-ordinates were taken at the top of 3 mound summits (Piddington, Lucy and Mila). These co-ordinates were used to georeference the map and subsequently draw 1 m-spaced, mound covering lines for mosaicking each of the 3 mounds.

These lines were flown while recording HD video and survey management was conducted in both Global Mapper and Qinsy where the ROV team could follow the flight plan in real time plotted over previously acquired bathymetric data (Lim et al., 2017). To maintain a clear image of the wreck surface, the ROV was flown <2 m from the mound surface at a survey speed of <0.3 knots. Several lights were attached to the ROV to achieve homogenous lighting across the camera field of view. All positioning data were stored as text files. .

Survey Log (UTC)

Tuesday 22nd & Wednesday 23rd April 2025

0900 vessel mobilisation begins (ROV and Geophysical Array). Whilst alongside in Galway, towed sensor equipment were mobilized, interfaced and verified.

Thursday 24th April 2025

1500 scientists board vessel
1530 vessel induction tour

Friday 25th April 2025

0030 pilot guides vessel out of Galway gates
0700 arrive at Rossaveel for ROV wet test
0740 ROV in water for testing
0815 ROV on deck. ROV continuously deployed and recovered for testing.
1040 ROV testing complete and transit to Station 1 (Geophysical Array deployment test)
1055 Geophysical Array deployment and acquisition for testing (**Station 1, Event 01**)
1245 Geophysical Array recovered to deck and transit to Wreck site 1 (SS Miami)
1645 Muster Drill during transit

Saturday 26th April 2025

0342 On site (SS Miami) for CTD (**Station 2, Event 01**)
0415 Geophysical Survey of SS Miami site (**Station 3, Event 01**). 3 Lines of Mag, SSS and MBES.
0530 Geophysical Array recovered to deck and transit to HMS Alyssum
0735 CTD (**Station 4**) at HMS Alyssum.
0745 CTD recovered to Deck

0810 Geophysical Survey of HMS Alyssum (**Station 5, Event 01**)
1030 Towed gear recovered to deck and transit to Wreck site 3 (U58)
1215 CTD in water (**Station 6, Event 01**) at U58
1225 CTD on deck, moving towards start of line for Geophysical Survey
1309 Geophysical Survey of U58 (**Station 7, Event 01**)
1500 Recover Geophysical array
1530 ROV in water at Wreck site 3 (U58) for **Station 7, Event 02 – Dive 1**
1546 ROV on bottom at U58

Sunday 27th April 2025

0032 ROV back on deck for reconfigure from oblique to downward facing camera to optimise visibility on top of the wreck
0349 ROV in water for downward-facing camera (**Station 7, Event 02 – Dive 2**)
0810 ROV on deck
0816 Grab sampling for U58 start
0816 Grab 1 no sample south of wreck (**Station 7, Event 03**)
0825 Grab 1 repeat south of wreck (**Station 7, Event 03**)
0845 Grab 2 north of wreck 0945 (**Station 7, Event 04**)
0908 Grab 3 control away from wreck (**Station 7, Event 05**)
0915 Transit to HMS Alyssum site
1146 On site (HMS Alyssum) and CTD in water (**Station 8, Event 01**)
1209 Start patch test at HMS Alyssum (**Station 8, Event 02**)
1346 ROV in water at HMS Alyssum (**Station 8, Event 03 – Dive 3**). Initial recon followed by survey lines.

Monday 28th April 2025

0229 ROV back on deck to reconfigure ROV for downward facing camera
0240 ROV back in water for downward facing camera (**Station 8, Event 03 – Dive 4**)
0706 End of Dive, ROV back on deck
0716 Grab sample for HMS Alyssum (**Station 8, Event 04**)
0729 Grab sample attempt - unsuccessful (**Station 8, Event 05**)
0735 Grab sample for HMS Alyssum (**Station 8, Event 05**)
0752 Grab sample for HMS Alyssum (**Station 8, Event 06**)
0755 Transit to Wreck site 1 (SS Miami)
0953 CTD deployment (**Station 9, Event 01**)
1042 ROV in water over SS Miami (**Station 9, Event 02 – Dive 5**)

Tuesday 29th April 2025

0138 ROV on deck after SS Miami Survey
0147 6 x Day Grab attempts with no success (**Station 9, Event 03**)
0250 Transit to start of Geophysical array line
1043 Start of Geophysical array line with EM2040 (**Station 10, Event 01**) deep tow cable across shelf and down slope over Macnas Mounds. Surveying continued from Macnas mounds towards deeper waters until the SSS LF channel stopped receiving a signal from the seafloor (~300 m water depth, ~280 m fish depth, 825 m cable out)
1439 Geophysical array recovered and EM2040 logging ended.

1644 Arrive on site (Piddington Mound location) and ROV deployed for reconnaissance survey to georeferenced the Moira Mound 10 cm bathymetric grid (**Station 11, Event 01 – Dive 6**).

Wednesday 30th April 2025

0058 ROV recovered to deck for inspection.

0214 ROV re-deployed to the Piddington Mound. Operations for ROV video mosaicking transects now conducted via Qinsy. Video surveying of Piddington Mound completed, and Lucy mound commenced.

Thursday 1st May 2025

Lucy mound completed and Mila mound surveying begins.

0511 Due to weather deterioration (wind speeds increasing ~40 knots and increasing swell), ROV recovered to deck. Given it is unlikely to get better and Geophysical operations limited to 330 m water depth from Magnetometers altimetry sensor, no further survey operations were required. Return to Galway port.

2045 Arrive at Galway gates, end of survey.

Key Results Summary

SM U-58: Site Assessment

Today (as of the 26th of April, 2025), the wreck of U-58 lies on the seafloor in an east-west orientation, with the vessel's bow pointed west. Much of U-58's outer hull is missing, with the exception of two intact sections amidship on either side and a small fragment on the starboard quarter. The larger midship sections likely correspond to ballast, regulator, and lubricating oil tanks. Similarly, the surface deck and associated falsework have also disappeared, and thus, most of what remains of the vessel is the pressure hull. The impact of net trawling is particularly evident at the wreck site, which has likely contributed to the increased deterioration of U-58. The vessel is draped in discarded fishing nets, particularly at the stern and bow, with the latter area featuring a considerable debris field.

Figure 13 Photogrammetric reconstruction of the starboard side of U-58

The starboard hydroplane is visible, though the aforementioned debris has made it difficult to discern if the port hydroplane is present. Both the fore and aft torpedo tubes are seen clearly extending from the ends of the pressure hull. A portion of the aft port tube has broken off and lays on the seafloor. Both screw assemblies, including the propellers, struts, and shafts, are intact. Signs of active corrosion are mainly present on south-facing port side of the pressure hull. A noticeable patch of orange rust on this surface (port quarter) appears associated with chafing from a large rope draped over the wreck that has disrupted the concretion layer. Forward of the intact outer hull portion on the port side, is a large section of black, graphitized steel, likely evidence of further destruction of the protective concretion. The remnants of bulkheads that divided the ballast and reserve fuel tanks can be seen along the exposed pressure hull. Likewise, various valves, vents, and piping used to transfer the contents of the external tanks are readily apparent in areas where the outer hull has broken off. Several large cylindrical objects, tentatively identified as air flasks, are seen strewn about the wreck site, including one lodged in an intact ballast tank on the port side. At amidship, the conning tower protrudes vertically into the water column, flanked by a periscope tube (forward) and a large exhaust duct (aft). Both deck guns are relatively intact, with the larger forward gun pointed up (~45°) and forward in the starboard direction. The aft gun is fixed in a similar orientation, though the barrel is level. There are two piles of cannisters, believed to ammunition for U-58's deck guns (Figure 13), situated between the guns and the conning tower.

Figure 14 Raw side scan image of U-58

HMS Alyssum: Site Assessment

In 2013, the Celtic Voyager surveyed the suspected wreck of HMS Alyssum using MBES as part of the CV13_02 survey leg. The results indicated that the ship had broken in two, with the main body of the vessel slightly south of the detached end. However, it was unclear if the broken section corresponded to the bow or stern. Furthermore, the wreck's identification could only be inferred by length and positioning, and thus, it was given the designation as "possibly" HMS Alyssum. As a result of the current survey effort, both of these ambiguities were definitively answered. During the ROV survey, the ship's nameplate, reading "ALY" was discovered at the southern end of the wreck site, confirming both the vessel's identity and its orientation. Close inspection of this portion, from the transom forward, revealed that wreck has undergone significant change in the last 12 years. When comparing MBES data collected this year with that from 2013, the stern section is considerably less upright. The ROV footage further supports this observation, as it appears that the stern has largely collapsed, indicated by broken deck plating that has slumped toward the port side. The ship's trawling winch, originally located on the upper deck of the stern quarter, has fallen to port, and rests less than two meters above the ground. Other indicators of this section's collapse include bollards on the seafloor, a suspected towing beam protruding out towards port (rather than being vertical), and deck beams that are perpendicular, instead of parallel, to the seafloor. The cause of this collapse is unknown, but with the absence of obvious trawling impacts, it is likely that a combination of currents, corrosion, and load-bearing stress (possibly associated with the weight of the steering engine at the ship's rear) are contributing factors. It is difficult to discern specific ship elements in this portion of wreckage, though it appears that one of the 3-pounder guns can be seen on the starboard side, detached from its mount. However, none of the other three guns could be identified.

Figure 15 ROV Image of the name plate of HMS Alyssum. Laser scale is 10 cm.

About 20 m forward of the transom, the hull is still intact, from the ship's floor up to the upper deck. Plating at the turn of the bilge is mainly present, except for several sections along the northwest-facing portside, which permits views of the ship's framing. A porthole, below the upper deck, can be seen clearly along the portside. At the upper deck level, the centre has caved in, likely corresponding to the space of the engine and boiler rooms, though neither piece of machinery is visible. The upper deck bulwarks, as well as the entire boat deck, are absent, giving the upper deck a mostly flat appearance. Furthermore, none of the ship's stacks or masts are visible, and thus, the upper deck and the debris

strewn across the intact portions of deck plating constitute the highest point of the wreck. It appears that the bow has broken off aft of the bridge, likely due to the damage inflicted by the mine that sunk *Alyssum*. The ship's floor, still connected to the main body of the wreck, continues forward from this break, though the ROV was unable to survey this area. What remains of the bow (the detached portion of wreckage to the north) is badly mangled, though one of the ship's bowser anchors (stockless) can be seen amongst the strewn debris. A section of intact deck plating can be seen along the northern part, with what appears to be either the ship's anchor windless or kedge reel.

Figure 16 Raw side scan image showing *HMS Alyssum*

SS Miami: Site Assessment

Based on the multibeam data for the wreck of *SS Miami*, it was obvious that the four boilers, arranged in two rows of two, and the engine constituted the highest point of the wreck. The ROV survey of the wreck further confirmed this observation. The fact that the ship's machinery stood higher than any other point means that the entirety of the vessel has collapsed around it, including the ship's coal bunkers. The cause of this collapse is purely speculative at this point, however, given its totality, it is possible that intentional destruction to lessen the wreck's status as a navigational hazard, either through wire dragging or detonation, may have occurred. Alternatively, *SS Miami's* location in an area of strong currents, likely responsible for the amount of exposed bedrock and lack of sedimentation, may have compromised the wreck's structural integrity. Increased water movement not only impacts sites through force but also exposes the steel structures to higher oxygen levels, exasperating corrosion through elevated exposure to oxygen (a primary driver of the steel corrosion process). These natural forces, combined with the load-bearing stress of such a large vessel, serve as plausible explanations to *SS Miami's* destruction, in the event wire dragging or detonation did not occur.

Figure 17 Raw bathymetric data showing SS Miami

While the wreck has maintained the general outline of the ship, it is exceedingly difficult at the present time to discern which elements are visible. Clearly identifiable components, such as one of the cargo winches could be seen, but the sheer amount of debris, representing four collapsed deck structures (laid flat), will require a lengthier time of analysis than currently permitted during the cruise. Additionally, the presence of specialized refrigeration machinery adds to the complexity involved of interpreting the SS Miami wreck site. Due to time constraints imposed by opportune weather windows, it was not possible to survey the 108 m long wreck in as much detail as the previous two wreck sites. Most of the ROV survey was spent on documenting the intact boilers and engine, in hopes of establishing a baseline assessment for future monitoring surveys.

Figure 18 Raw side scan image data showing SS Miami

ROV Video Photogrammetry of Piddington, Lucy and Mila Mounds

Three downward-facing ROV HD video survey grids were acquired within the downslope area of the Moira Mounds region. Each grid was approximately 50 x 50 m with transect lines spaced 1 m apart. The ROV maintained an altitude of 2 m above the seafloor and a speed of approximately 0.4 knots. USBL navigation and INS attitude data were recorded during all dives. Each grid covered the surface of an individual mound in addition to the local off-mound habitat resulting in complete coverage of two CWC mounds and partial coverage of a third mound. In total, approximately 40 hours of video data were collected across an area of approximately 7500 m². Data will be used to construct 3D photogrammetric models of each mound to examine local-scale differences in the ecological composition and the distribution of reef framework across the mound surfaces, and to build upon datasets collected previously.

The first grid was acquired from Piddington Mound which has been fully characterized and repeatedly surveyed. Thus, the data collected here will be used to compare against previous findings, building upon an important temporal dataset within a CWC mound habitat. The second grid was acquired from a mound approximately 50 m southeast of Piddington Mound. Benthic landers previously measured current speed, direction, and temperature from the northern and southern end of this mound. The third mound was located approximately 70 m to the southwest of Piddington Mound and this is the first time that video-data were collected at this mound.

Although these three mounds are in close proximity, preliminary review of the video-data indicate that their biological composition may vary. Video data show that all three mounds consist of dense live coral framework (*Lophelia pertusa* [*syn. Desmophyllum pertusum*] and *Madrepora oculata*), dead coral framework, coral rubble, and rippled sands. In addition to the coral framework, numerous glass sponges (*Aphrocallistes beatrix*), octocorals, antipatharians, echinoids (*Gracilechinus* spp. and *Cidaris cidaris*), squat lobsters, carrier crabs, and fish (e.g. *Lepidion eques* and *Heliocolenus dactylopterus*) were observed. Live coral cover ranged from sparse near the flanks and edges to dense near the summit. Off-mound habitats at each site were often comprised of dropstones, as well two common off-mound species, *Psolus squamatus* and *Pliobothrus symmetricus*.

Figure 19 Example images collected from the various mounds surveyed. Post-survey analysis will be carried out on the full data set.

Figure 20 ROV-video photogrammetry survey grid acquired from three differing mounds showing the position of the newly-named Mila and Lucy mounds relative to the Piddington Mound studied by Lim *et al* (2017). Scale: transect lines were spaced 1 m apart.

Magnetometry Data

Magnetometry data were acquired via piggyback configuration over the three shipwrecks using a Geometrics G-882 cesium vapor magnetometer. Three lines per shipwreck were acquired at 5 m altitude. The magnetometer is a scalar magnetometer measuring the total strength of the magnetic field (B_0) that it experiences. To remove noise, the total magnetic field is smoothed using a running mean within a window of 20 data points. Additionally, we estimate the ambient magnetic field (\bar{B}) from B_0 , using a running mean with a window size of 2000 data points. Using B_0 and \bar{B} , we calculate the magnetic residual $B_0 - \bar{B}$, where any magnetic anomaly will be depicted as deviation from 0. For each recorded line, we depict the raw value of B_0 in red, the smoothed value of B_0 in black and \bar{B} in grey. The estimated residuals are depicted as black curves. Furthermore, we combined all lines per shipwreck and linearly interpolated the residuals on a grid. This yields a 2D heat map, where the line points of the raw data are indicated as black dots.

Figure 21 3-line traces for survey lines acquired over the HMS Alyssum showing total magnetic field (above) and residual field (below)

Figure 22 3-line traces for survey lines acquired over the SS Miami showing total magnetic field (above) and residual field (below)

Figure 23 3-line traces for survey lines acquired over U58 showing total magnetic field (above) and residual field (below)

Figure 24 Residual magnetic grid for U-58, SS Miami and HMS Alyssum

Appendices

Personnel

Scientific complement

Dr Aaron Lim	Chief Scientist	Survey management, scientific direction, reporting, project management and liaison	UCC
Dr Larissa de Oliveira	Day shift Leader	Data manager, team lead for day shift operations, ROV video backup lead	UCC
Ms Corie Boolukos	Night Shift Leader	Team leader for night shift operations, lead for marine biology	UCC
Mr Ruaihri Strachan	Scientist and Technical Lead	Technical survey lead, survey mobilisation, engineering and interfacing, online survey manager	UCC/Green Rebel
Dr Ger Summers	Survey Geoscientist	GIS Lead, online surveying (Geophysics, Hydrography and Video), data processing	UCC
Dr Dominic Bush	Survey Archaeologist	Marine archaeologist, online surveying (Geophysics, Hydrography and Video), sediment sampling	UCC
Mr Kevin Walsh	Geoscientist	Online surveying (Geophysics, Hydrography and Video) and GIS, sediment sampling, data processing	UCC
Ms Cara Brennan	Geoscientist	Online surveying (Geophysics, Hydrography and Video), sediment sampling, data processing, survey engineering	UCC
Mr Luca Caminiti	Scientist	Online surveying (Geophysics, Hydrography and Video) and MMO, sediment sampling	UCC
Mr Frank Bastian	Scientist	Online surveying (Magnetometry and Video), sediment sampling	UCC
Ms Irene Loriga	Scientist	Online surveying (Video), sediment sampling	UCC
Ms Bonnie Young	Scientist	Online surveying (Video), sediment sampling	UCC
Mr Julian O' Malley	Scientist	Online surveying (Geophysics, Hydrography and Video), sediment sampling	UCC

Holland 1 ROV pilots

Mr Paddy O' Driscoll (ROV Superintendent)	Mr George Findley
Mr Kyle Carr	Mr Arnie McNaugher
Mr William Phelps	Mr Artjoms Gozins

Officers and Crew of RV Celtic Explorer

Captain Anthony Hobin	Master
Mr Paddy Kenny	Chief Officer and Security Officer
Mr Duirmuid Joyce	2 nd Officer and Safety Officer
Mr John Sammon	Chief Engineer
Mr Fintan Keating	2 nd Engineer
Mr Gerard O Connell	ETO
Mr Tom Gilmartin	Bosun
Mr Anthony Hill	Cook
Mr Martin Powell	Bosuns Mate
Mr Tommy Grealy	AB Deckhands

Mr Peter Joyce	AB Deckhands
Mr Ian Murphy	Technician
Mr Nigel Dowd	AB Deckhand
Mr Eoin Colfer	AB Deckhand
Mr Paul Comberford	Asst. Cook
Mr Patrick Morris	Technician

Left to right: Aaron Lim, Cara Brennan, Dominic Bush, Corie Boolukos, Frank Bastian, Larissa De Oliveira, Julian O Malley, Luca Caminiti, Ger Summers, Kevin Walsh, Ruaihri Strachan, Bonnie Young, Irene Loriga

Stations (Logs and maps)

Master Log Sheet

Master Log sheet				Time (UTC)	DDM		Tick appropriate Event						Note	
Station	Event #	Dive #	Date		Lat	Long	Depth (m)	CTD	ROV Video	EM2040	Magnometry	SSS		Grab
1	1		25_04	10:55	53°11.520	09°39.54	48.3			X				Test
1	1		25_04	12:15	53°06.57	09°53.75	91.7			X	X	X		Test (SSS, Mag, MBES)
2	1		26_04	03:42	51°23.14	09°17.39	66.2	X						CTD deployed to 10m, recovered, redeployed fully
3	1		26_04	04:15	52°23.50	09°15.74	63.7			X	X	X		Wreck 1 (SSS, Mag, MBES) Line 1, USBL dropping a lot
3	1		26_04	04:42	51°24.28	09°14.63	~63			X	X	X		Wreck 1, Line 2
3	1		26_04	05:19	51°23.23	09°16.19	63.2			X	X	X		Wreck 1, Line 3 (redoing Line 1)
4	1		26_04	07:35	51°29.78	08°48.64	73.4	x						CTD deployed to 10m, recovered, redeployed fully
5	1		26_04	08:10	51°29.51	08°48.10	77			x	x	x		Wreck 2 (SSS, Mag, MBES), Line 1
5	1		26_04	08:46	51°30.54	08°47.07	70			x	x	x		Wreck 2 - Line 2 - Slightly Offset Due to changing surving planning
5	1		26_04	09:26	51°29.51	08°48.08	76			x	x	x		Wreck 2 - Line 3
6	1		26_04	12:15	51°36.25	08°12.37	75	x						CTD deployed to 10m, recovered, redeployed fully
7	1		26_04	13:09	51°36.21	08°11.18	77.1			x	x	x		Wreck3 - L1
7	1		26_04	13:25	51°36.46	08°08.71	79.7			x	x	x		Wreck3 - L2
7	1		26_04	14:40	51°36.27	08°11.12	78.4			x	x	x		Wreck3 - L3
7	2		26_04	15:46	51°36.34	08°09.94	77		X					ROV wreck3 in the water
7	2		27_04	00:32	51°36.31	08°09.93	75		X					ROV on deck
7	2		27_04	03:49	51°36.31	08°09.93	77		X					ROV in water -> Wreck 3
7	3		27_04	08:16	51°36.332	8°9.907	80.4						X	Attempt not succesful
7	3		27_04	08:25	51°36.326	8°9.903	80.6						X	Muddy sand some clay pallets - no smell
7	4		27_04	08:45	51°36.228	8°9.523	80						X	Silty sand some clay pallets - no smell
7	5		27_04	09:08	51°36.286	8°10.01	81						X	Muddy sand some clay pallets - no smell
8			27_04	11:46	51°30.10	8°47.43	71	X						CTD deployed to 10m, recovered, redeployed fully
8	2		27_04	12:09	51°30.051	08°47.625	77.9			X				Line 1 - Patch test 4kn
8	2		27_04	12:23	51°30.08	08°47.35	72.6			X				Line 2 - Patch test 4kn
8	2		27_04	12:37	51°30.09	08°47.69	72.5			X				Line 3 - Patch test 4kn
8	2		27_04	12:54	51°29.95	08°47.39	74.7			X				Line 4 - Patch test 4kn
8	2		27_04	13:13	51°30.10	08°47.72	74			X				Line 5 Patch test 8kn

Master Log sheet				Time (UTC)	DDM		Tick appropriate Event						Note	
Station	Event #	Dive #	Date		Lat	Long	Depth (m)	CTD	ROV Video	EM2040	Magnometry	SSS		Grab
8	2		27_04	13:13	51°30.10	08°47.72	74			X				Line 5 Patch test 8kn
8	3		27_04	13:46	51°29.95	08°47.35	76.7		X					ROV in water - test dive. ROV spotted at 3.40pm
8	3		27_04	16:30	51°29.98	08°47.59	78.6		X					Strt of video survey of Alyssum
8	3		27_04	20:41	51°39.0	08°47.68	74.4		X					Start of N side of Alyssum
8	3		28_04	02:24	51°30.04	08.47.54	72.2		X					ROV on deck - End Alyssum dive (N.15 oblique dives)
8	3		28_04	02:40	51°30.09	08°47.59	71.3		X					ROV in water Alyssum for downward facing lines
8	3		28_04	07:06	51°30.03	08°47.54	74.6		X					ROV on deck - end of Alyssum top lines
8	4		28_04	07:16	51°30.2621	8°47.53285	81.5					X		CTD cast
8	5		28_04	07:29	51°30.03863	8°47.59299	82					X		Attempt not succesful
8	5		28_04	07:35	51°30.03885	8°47.59422	80.6					X		Sandy Mud, no smell
8	6		28_04	07:52	51°29.95412	8°47.66010	81.1					X		Sandy Mud
9	1		28_04	09:52	51°23.65	09°15.51	60.3	X						CTD cast
9	2		28_04	10:42	51°23.70	09°15.42	59.8		X					ROV in the water test dive
9	2		28_04	18:55	51°23.75	09°15.42	63.3		X					ROV stop- line plan reconfiguring, adjusting global mapper
9	2		28_04	19:16	51°23.72	09°15.39	63.9		X					ROV Stop- recon on boilers with new grid, restarting
9	2		28_04	01:38	51°23.76	09°15.14	58.6		X					ROV on deck - end Miami dive
9	3		29_04	01:47	51°23.74	09°15.38	62.9					X		Start of sediment sampling at Miami - all sediment sampling attempts were unsuccessful due to presence of bedrock
10	1		29_04	10:43	51°27.57	11°13.07	195.2			X	X	X		Transit Geophysics Survey
10	1		29_04	14:39	51°28.04	11°33.89	450			X	X	X		End of lines - too deep for MBES/SSS. Transiting to coral mounds
11	1		6_29_04	16:44	51°29.79°	11°49.12°	963		x					ROV in water
11	1		6_29_04	17:40	51°29.72°	11°49.01°	967		x					ROV recon of Piddington to georeference the map- started logging ROV USBL location in Quinsy

CE25006 Cruise Report: ROV Monitoring Survey

Master Log sheet				Time	DDM	DDM	Tick appropriate Event								
Station	Event #	Dive #	Date	(UTC)	Lat	Long	Depth (m)	CTD	ROV	Video	EM2040	Magnometry	SSS	Grab	Note
11	1	6	29_04	00:58	51°29.61°	11°49.11°	963.7			x					ROV on deck - recovered for INS repairs
11	1	7	30_04	02:14	51°29.68°	11°49.07°	963.7			x					ROV in water - Start of Piddington Mound Grid again
12	1	7	30_04	12:44	51°29.64°	11°49.11°	963.7			x					Start of grid at East of Piddington Mound
13	1	7	01_05	01:14	51°29.68°	11°49.18°	961.4			x					Start of grid at West of Piddington small mound
13	1	7	01_05	05:11	51°29.68°	11°49.18°	963.7			x					ROV on deck

Video Log sheets

Date: 26/05/2025 Dive number: 1

Station #	Event #	Dive #	Line #	ROV On Bottom (UTC)	Video Start Time (UTC)	Video End Time (UTC)	Time Video KIPRO change or stop	Lasers On? (Y/N)	Depth (m)	Start Latitude (DDM)	Start Longitude (DDM)	End Latitude (DDM)	End Longitude (DDM)	HD Cameras Used	Data Backed Up? (Y/N)	Notes
7	3	1	N1.5		16:53	17:23		Y	76.9	51°36.3	08°09.95	51°36.3	08°09.89	Y	Y	North line at 2am offbottom
										51°36.3		51°36.3				Repeat of first line to assess current direction. Poor visibility against current -> decision to move w current. ~17:35 caught on rope
7	3	1	N3		17:25	17:42		Y	76.9	51°36.3	08°09.90	51°36.3	08°09.91	Y	Y	
7	3	1	N4		17:46	18:03		Y	76.9	51°36.3	08°09.91	51°36.3	08°09.88	Y	Y	
7	3	1	N5		18:13	18:24		Y	76.4	51°36.3	08°09.91	51°36.3	08°09.88	Y	Y	
7	3	1	N6		18:27	18:36		Y	73.7	51°36.3	08°09.88	51°36.3	08°09.90	Y	Y	Start E -> W. 18:32 down to 4 W->E
							CHANGED BEFORE START LINE	Y	75.8	51°36.3	08°09.86	51°36.3	08°09.92	Y	Y	E-> W; Reposition @ 19:31; Full stop @ 19:21; Lots of sediment; Altitude fluctuating (up to 3m) @ 19:25; line still paused @ 19:39; Redo? (ask at end); Did at 2m ALT instead of 1.5
7	3	1	S1.5		19:02	20:08		Y	76.2	51°36.3	08°09.88	51°36.3	08°09.93	Y	Y	E->W; 20:27 moved slightly away to avoid net
							CHANGED BEFORE START LINE	Y	73.2	51°36.3	08°09.88	51°36.3	08°09.93	Y	Y	21:21:10 crab sighted
7	3	1	S3		20:59	21:23		Y	73.4	51°36.3	08°09.89	51°36.3	08°09.93	Y	Y	E->W
7	3	1	S4		21:39	21:59		Y	73.1	51°36.3	08°09.88	51°36.3	08°09.93	Y	Y	E->W; 22:24 turned away from wreck to avoid rope
7	3	1	S5		22:11	22:34		Y	74.1	51°36.3	08°09.88	51°36.3	08°09.94	Y	Y	Sonar not picking ship due to high altitude; E-> W; Fighting currents; 23:16 camera tilted downwards & zoomed in; there was slight unintentional camera manipulation before this; 23:14 the ship was moving in the opposite direction (not currents before)
							CHANGED BEFORE START LINE	Y	74.4	51°36.3	08°09.93	51°36.3	08°09.93	Y	Y	Line aborted-video data not good. Decided to recover ROV to reposition camera to downward facing
7	3	1	B17		00:00	00:08		Y	73.9	51°36.3	08°09.93	MISSING	MISSING	Y	Y	ROV recovery started

Dive number: 2

Station #	Event #	Dive #	Line #	ROV On Bottom (UTC)	Video Start Time (UTC)	Video End Time (UTC)	Time Video KIPRO change or stop	Lasers On? (Y/N)	Depth (m)	Start Latitude (DDM)	Start Longitude (DDM)	End Latitude (DDM)	End Longitude (DDM)	HD Cameras Used	Data Backed Up? (Y/N)	Notes
7	3	2	NA	04:00	04:41	NA		NA	77.2	51°36.32	08°09.93	NA	NA	Y		To much debris - Start w/ HD camera fixed To ROV bottom - moving sideways, not on line yet - looking for best place
7	3	2	B12		04:48	06:22	KIPRO stop	Y	77.3	51°36.32	08°09.93	51°36.33	08°09.89	Y	multiple	Start line - bad vis passes - difficulto to differentiate different lines
7	3	2	E5		06:28	06:51		Y	77	51°36.33	08°09.89	51°36.32	08°09.90	Y		length of ship -> W - Center line
7	3	2	W3		06:53	07:07		Y	77.2	51°36.33	08°09.90	51°36.33	08°09.90	Y		South of central line W->E - issues with auto depth dragging the ROV up or down during passes
7	3	2	E7		07:12	07:33	Last KIPRO	Y	76	51°36.33	08°09.89	51°36.32	08°09.91	Y		ROV going backwards to clear paths - Stop recording

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Date:		27-28_04_25		Dive number:		3											
Station #	Event #	Dive #	Line #	ROV On Bottom (UTC)	Video Start Time (UTC)	Video End Time (UTC)	Time Video KIPRO change or stop	Lasers On? (Y/N)	Depth (m)	Start Latitude (DDM)	Start Longitude (DDM)	End Latitude (DDM)	End Longitude (DDM)	HD Cameras Used	Data Backed Up? (Y/N)	Notes	
8	3	3	S1.5	Y	16:33:58	17:02:02		Y	82	51°21.98	08°47.59	51°30.01	08°47.54	Y	Y		
8	3	3	S3		17:22:50	17:41:18		Y	78	51°29.99	08°47.58	51°30.01	08°47.54	Y	Y		
8	3	3	S4		17:58	18:25	Changed k	Y	76.5	51°29.98	08°49.59	51°30.01	08°49.53	Y	Y	Camera moved 18:22	
8	3	3	S5		18:45	18:49	Start kipro	Y	75.9	51°29.99	08°47.56	51°30.00	08°47.51	Y	Y	Top of the wreck 5m	
8	3	3	N1.5		20:46	20:59		Y	73.9	51°30.00	08°47.63	51°30.03	08°47.60	Y	Y	S->N	
8	3	3	N3		21:20	21:42		Y	74.6	51°30.01	08°47.63	51°30.03	08°47.59	Y	Y		
8	3	3	N4		22:04	22:22		Y	72.5	51°30.00	08°47.62	51°30.04	08°47.55	Y	Y	Altitude less than 4 for most; about 3.7 to 3.8	
8	3	3	N4.5		22:43	23:00	Kipro stop	Y	73.1	51°30.10	08°47.61	51°30.04	08°47.55	Y	Y		
8	3	3	N5		23:01	23:18		Y	71.9	51.30033	8.475644	51°30.02	08°47.62	Y	Y	Start coordinates were taken from composite as original screen	
8	3	3	BBN2		23:39	00:13	Kirpro chan	Y	75.4	51°36.04	08°47.59	51°30.05	08°47.55	Y	Y	Was obscured EOL was done using the normal	
8	3	3	BBN2.5		00:13	00:22		Y	70.6	51°30.05	08°47.55	51°30.40	08°47.57	Y	Y		
8	3	3	BBN3		00:22	00:33		Y	70.3	51°30.40	08°47.57	51°30.40	08°47.57	Y	Y		
8	3	3	BBN4		00:33	00:41		Y	71.8	51°30.50	08°47.37	51°30.40	08°47.57	Y	Y		
8	3	3	BBS1.5		01:10	01:20		Y	69.9	51°30.04	08°47.54	51°30.04	08°47.54	Y	Y	E->W	
8	3	3	BBs 2.5		01:22	01:25		Y	71.5	51°30.04	08°47.54	51°30.04	08°47.54	Y	Y		
8	3	3	BBS 3		01:25	01:35	kipro chan	Y	71.7	51°30.04	08°47.54	51°30.04	08°47.54	Y	Y		

		Dive		4											
Station #	Event #	Dive #	Line #	Video Start Time (UTC)	Video End Time (UTC)	Time Video KIPRO change or stop	Lasers On? (Y/N)	Depth (m)	Start Latitude (DDM)	Start Longitude (DDM)	End Latitude (DDM)	End Longitude (DDM)	HD Cameras Used	Data Backed Up? (Y/N)	Notes
8	3	4	WC1	03:27	03:58		N	76.5	51°30.01	08°47.56	51°30.01	08°47.56	Y	Y	START DOWNWARD FACING DIVE
8	3	4	W2	04:00	04:15		N	76	51°30.01	08°47.56	51°30.01	08°47.56	Y	Y	laser scalers turned on half way thru line
8	3	4	W3	04:16	04:33		Y	75.9	51°30.01	08°47.56	51°30.01	08°47.56	Y	Y	
8	3	4	E1	04:35	04:51	kipro chan	Y	77	51°30.01	08°47.56	51°30.01	08°47.56	Y	Y	
8	3	4	TB 1	04:58	05:56		Y	76.1	51°30.01	08°47.56	51°30.01	08°47.56	Y	Y	05:49 - text ALY on hull. 05:20 - toilet seat
8	3	4	BBB 1	06:07	06:11		Y	76.4	51°30.02	08°47.55	51°30.03	08°47.54	Y	Y	SW->NE; line down center of wreck - broken bit of wreck
8	3	4	BBT1	06:12	06:15		Y	74	51°30.03	08°47.54	51°30.03	08°47.54	Y	Y	NE->SW
8	3	4	BBB 2	06:17	06:20		Y	75.3	51°30.03	08°47.54	51°30.03	08°47.54	Y	Y	SW->NE @ 1.5 altitude; line on the lower side of the wreck
8	3	4	BBE1	06:23	00:00		Y	73.9	51°30.03	08°47.54	51°30.03	08°47.54	Y	Y	lines were done going forwards and then backwards across the wreck in two passes (SW->NE & NE->SW; reposition @ 6:27; altitude = 2m; after this one continuous forward facing line was done zigzagging over SW->NE @ varying altitudes; 6:42 ROV touched the seafloor in between the break before doing lines to view both sides of the break

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Dive 5															
Station #	Event #	Dive #	Line #	Video Start Time (UTC)	Video End Time (UTC)	Time Video KIPRO change or stop	Lasers On? (Y/N)	Depth (m)	Start Latitude (DDM)	Start Longitude (DDM)	End Latitude (DDM)	End Longitude (DDM)	HD Cameras Used	Data Backed Up? (Y/N)	Notes
9	2	5	NA	10:47	MISSING		MISSING	59.8	51°23.70	09°15.42	MISSING	MISSING	MISSING	Y	ROV in water - Test Dive
														Y	no altitude changes in lines given the wreck is flat
9	2	5	S1	13:34	13:50		Y	56.9	51°23.77	09°15.37	51°23.73	09°15.44	Y	Y	wreck part way down the line and then started again at 14:14
9	2	5	S2	14:08	14:30		Y	57.7	51°23.76	09°15.39	51°23.72	09°15.45	Y	Y	ROV Stop 15:06 line aborted
9	2	5	S3	15:02	15:06		Y	56.7	51°23.77	09°15.38				Y	
9	2	5	S3	15:35	15:52	change K	Y	64.9	51°23.76	09°15.36	51°23.73	09°15.40	Y	Y	
9	2	5	S4	16:11	16:31		Y	63.5	51°23.77	09°15.33	51°23.75	09°15.40	Y	Y	
9	2	5	S5	16:57	17:15		Y	62.9	51°23.77	09°15.34	51°23.74	09°15.40	Y	Y	
9	2	5	S6	17:32	17:48		Y	62.6	51°23.77	09°15.35	51°23.74	09°15.40	Y	Y	
														Y	Boilers found and offset confirmed - Dive stopped to reassess the offset. Imago to be fixed in global mapper
9	2	5	S7	17:58	18:22		Y	64.1	51°23.76	09°15.37	51°23.73	09°15.40	Y	Y	South of NE1, camera move at 23:27, boiler at 23:36 and 23:38
9	2	5	NE1	23:11	23:25		Y	56	51°23.75	09°15.42	51°23.76	09°15.41	y	Y	south of sw1; boiler at 23:53; engine at 23:56
9	2	5	NE2	23:49	00:03		y	54.4	51°23.76	09°15.41	51°23.75	09°15.43	y	Y	in between ne1 and sw1
9	2	5	SW2	00:08	00:18		y	54.4	51°23.75	09°15.43	51°23.76	09°15.41	y	Y	continuous lines over boilers and engine; at 00:53, currents causing bouncing
9	2	5	BE1	00:22	00:58		y	56.3	51.23.76	09°15.47	51°23.76	09°15.41	Y	Y	

Dive number: 6															
Event #	Dive #	Line #	ROV On Bottom (UTC)	Video Start Time (UTC)	Video End Time (UTC)	Time Video KIPRO change or stop	Lasers On? (Y/N)	Depth (m)	Start Latitude (DDM)	Start Longitude (DDM)	End Latitude (DDM)	End Longitude (DDM)	HD Cameras Used	Data Backed Up? (Y/N)	Notes
1	6			18:15	19:41:42	Change at 2	Y	963.3	51°29.77	11°49.08	51°29.70	011°49.05	Y	Y	Reckon dive for georeferencing of Pidington Mound area. ROV recovered to deck to fix USBL

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Dive 7													
Dive #	Line #	Video Start Time (UTC)	Video End Time (UTC)	Time Video KIPRO change or stop	Lasers On? (Y/N)	Depth (m)	Start Latitude (DDM)	Start Longitude (DDM)	End Latitude (DDM)	End Longitude (DDM)	HD Camera as Used	Data Backed Up? (Y/N)	Notes
													Issue with gyro (INS), ROV recovered and redeployed. Grid started from the North side of the Piddington Mound
7	1TN	03:19	03:29		Y	963.3	51°29.77	11°49.04	51°29.70	11°49.05	Y	Y	
7	2BN	03:30	03:44		Y	959.7	51°29.77	11°49.11	51°29.71	11°49.11	Y	Y	
7	3TN	03:45	03:53		Y	959.7	51°29.71	11°49.11	51°29.71	11°49.11	Y	Y	USBL unstable
7	4BN	03:55	04:01		Y	959.7	51°29.72	11°49.11	51°29.71	11°49.11	Y	Y	North to South Q22 S; Altitude 1.5 metres
7	5TN	04:08	04:20		Y	959.7	51°29.73	11°49.11	51°29.71	11°49.11	Y	Y	Moving backward; 3.59 spider crab
7	6BN	04:20	04:36		Y	963.6	51°29.74	11°49.11	51°29.71	11°49.11	Y	Y	
7	8TN	04:36	04:48		Y	963.6	51°29.75	11°49.11	51°29.71	11°49.11	Y	Y	
7	9BN	04:48	05:02		Y	963.6	51°29.76	11°49.11	51°29.71	11°49.11	Y	Y	
7	10TN	05:04	05:21	change before line	Y	963.6	51°29.77	11°49.11	51°29.71	11°49.11	Y	Y	
7	11BN	05:26	05:39		Y	963.6	51°29.78	11°49.11	51°29.71	11°49.11	Y	Y	
7	12TN	05:41	05:52		Y	963.6	51°29.79	11°49.11	51°29.71	11°49.11	Y	Y	
7	13BN	05:53	06:00		Y	963.6	51°29.80	11°49.11	51°29.71	11°49.11	Y	Y	Far above seabed - bad lines
7	14TN	06:02	06:12		Y	963.6	51°29.81	11°49.11	51°29.71	11°49.11	Y	Y	
7	14BN	06:14	06:22		Y	936.6	51°29.71	11°49.11	51°29.71	11°49.11	Y	Y	
7	15TN	06:23	06:34		Y	936.7	51°29.71	11°49.11	51°29.71	11°49.11	Y	Y	
7	16BN	06:35	06:44		Y	963.7	51°29.72	11°49.11	51°29.71	11°49.11	Y	Y	
7	17TN	06:45	06:56		Y	963.7	51°29.72	11°49.11	51°29.71	11°49.11	Y	Y	
7	18TN	07:01	07:08	Kipro change @start of lines	Y	963.6	51°29.71	11°49.11	51°29.71	11°49.11	Y	Y	Double back on N-S lines from northern end of mound
7	19BN	07:09	MISSING		Y	964.5	51°29.71	MISSING	MISSING	MISSING	Y	Y	Aborted- call to south
7	19BS	07:44	07:57		Y	965.9	51°29.65	11°49.12	51°29.65	11°49.12	Y	Y	
7	20TS	07:58	08:07		Y	962.2	51°29.65	11°49.12	51°29.65	11°49.12	Y	Y	
7	21BS	08:08	08:17		Y	965.1	51°29.65	11°49.12	51°29.65	11°49.12	Y	Y	
7	22TS	08:18	08:25		Y	980.8	51°29.65	11°49.12	51°29.65	11°49.12	Y	Y	
7	23BS	08:26	08:36		Y	964.8	51°29.65	11°49.12	51°29.65	11°49.12	Y	Y	
7	24TS	08:38	08:45		Y	957.8	51°29.65	11°49.12	51°29.65	11°49.12	Y	Y	
7	25BS	08:47	08:56		Y	964	51°29.65	11°49.12	51°29.65	11°49.12	Y	Y	
7	26TS	08:58	09:11	9:00 (change)	Y	952	51°29.65	11°49.12	51°29.65	11°49.12	Y	Y	
7	26BS	09:12	09:27		Y	952	51°29.65	11°49.12	51°26.65	11°49.12	Y	Y	Redo line 26TS
7	27TS	09:28	09:38		Y	967	51°29.65	11°49.12	51°26.65	11°49.12	Y	Y	
7	28BS	09:39	09:49		Y	963	51°29.65	11°49.12	51°26.65	11°49.12	Y	Y	
7	29TS	09:52	10:00		Y	963	51°29.65	11°49.12	51°29.65	11°49.12	Y	Y	
7	30BS	10:07	10:16		Y	968	51°29.65	11°49.10	51°29.65	11°49.10	Y	Y	
7	31TS	10:17	10:27		Y	963	51°29.65	11°49.10	51°29.65	11°49.10	Y	Y	
7	32BS	10:28	10:38		Y	963	51°29.65	11°49.10	51°29.65	11°49.10	Y	Y	Oreofish (10:38)
7	33TS	10:39	10:47		Y	965	51°29.65	11°49.10	51°29.65	11°49.10	Y	Y	Scorpion fish (10:42) (10:46)
7	34BS	10:51	10:58	10:50 (change)	Y	963	51°29.65	11°49.10	51°29.65	11°49.10	Y	Y	
7	35TS	11:00	11:03		Y	963	51°29.65	11°49.10	51°29.65	11°49.10	Y	Y	

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7	36BS	11:11	11:18	11:20 (change)	Y	963	51°29.65	11°49.10	51°29.65	11°49.10	Y	Y	Redo in centre line
7	37BS	11:25	11:35		Y	963.7	51°29.65	11°49.10	51°29.64	11°49.10	Y	Y	Additional coverage in centre
7	control	12:04	12:20		Y	963.7	51°29.65	11°49.11	51°29.64	11°49.10	Y	Y	USBL snailtrail frozen @ 11:50 AM, fixed @12PM, octopus @12:11, rock outcrop @12:10
7	no line	MISSING	12:44	12:44	Y	963.7	51°29.64	11°49.11	51°29.64	11°49.11	Y	Y	KIPRO change before start of grid
7	TN1	12:47	12:55		Y	963.7	51°29.64	11°49.11	51°29.64	11°49.11	Y	Y	Start of grid, new kipro
7	BN2	13:01	13:05		Y	963.7	51°29.65	11°49.11	51°29.64	11°49.11	Y	Y	
7	TN3	13:09	13:16		Y	963.7	51°29.64	11°49.11	51°29.64	11°49.11	Y	Y	
7	BN4	13:19	13:27		Y	963.7	51°29.64	11°49.11	51°29.65	11°49.11	Y	Y	
7	TN5	13:30	13:41		Y	963.7	51°29.65	11°49.11	51°29.65	11°49.11	Y	Y	Starting mapping each line starting from north, then back up same line from south
7	BN6	13:42	13:45		Y	963.7	51°29.64	11°49.11	51°29.65	11°49.11	Y	Y	Same line as TN5, but starting at south
7	TN7	13:49	13:54		Y	963.7	51°29.65	11°49.11	51°29.65	11°49.11	Y	Y	
7	BN8	13:54	13:56		Y	963.7	51°29.65	11°49.11	51°29.65	11°49.11	Y	Y	
7	TN9	13:59	14:08		Y	963.7	51°29.65	11°49.11	51°29.65	11°49.11	Y	Y	
7	BN10	14:08	14:10		Y	963.6	51°29.65	11°49.11	51°29.65	11°49.11	Y	Y	
7	TN11	14:12	14:19		Y	963.6	51°29.65	11°49.11	51°29.65	11°49.11	Y	Y	
7	TN12	14:25	14:30		Y	963.9	51°29.65	11°49.11	51°29.65	11°49.11	Y	Y	No view of coral on trackback from south. Naming line North only from now on
7	TN13	14:34	14:40		Y	967.1	51°29.65	11°49.11	51°29.65	11°49.11	Y	Y	ROV speed picking up when approaching mound
7	TN14	14:50	14:56	14:44	Y	968.4	51°29.65	11°49.11	51°29.65	11°49.11	Y	Y	Kipro change @ 14:44
7	TN15	15:01	15:09		Y	963.7	51°29.65	11°49.11	51°29.65	11°49.11	Y	Y	
7	TN16	15:12	15:19		Y	967.9	51°29.65	11°49.11	51°29.65	11°49.11	Y	Y	
7	TN17	15:24	15:31		Y	967.8	51°29.65	11°49.11	51°29.65	11°49.10	Y	Y	
7	TN18	15:35	15:42		Y	968.1	51°29.65	11°49.11	51°29.65	11°49.10	Y	Y	
7	TN19	15:46	15:55		Y	965.1	51°29.65	11°49.10	51°29.65	11°49.10	Y	Y	
7	TN20	16:02	16:11		Y	967.1	51°29.65	11°49.10	51°29.65	11°49.10	Y	Y	
7	TN21	16:18	16:26		Y	967.7	51°29.65	11°49.10	51°29.66	11°49.10	Y	Y	Broke Coral @ 16:22
7	TN22	16:32	16:41	16:42 change	Y	967.1	51°29.66	11°49.10	51°29.66	11°49.10	Y	Y	
7	TN23	16:45	16:54		Y	963.7	51°29.66	11°49.10	51°29.66	11°49.10	Y	Y	
7	TN24	16:59	17:05		Y	963.9	51°29.66	11°49.10	51°29.66	11°49.10	Y	Y	ROV passed on top of same plastic bag for the third time
7	TN25	17:11	17:18		Y	963.9	51°29.66	11°49.10	51°29.66	11°49.10	Y	Y	
7	TN26	17:24	17:32		Y	963.9	51°29.66	11°49.09	51°29.66	11°49.09	Y	Y	
7	TN27	17:35	17:45		Y	965.9	51°29.66	11°49.09	51°29.66	11°49.09	Y	Y	Potential black golve @ 17:36. Massive polips coral framework
7	TN28	17:50	17:52		Y	963.7	51°29.66	11°49.09	51°29.66	11°49.09	Y	Y	
7	TN29	18:03	18:13		Y	963.7	51°29.66	11°49.08	51°29.67	11°49.07	Y	Y	Water bottle @ 18:06 massive polip corals spotted again
7	TN30	#####	18:24		Y	963.7	51°29.67	11°49.07	51°29.67	11°49.07	Y	Y	Plactic bottle @ 18:32
7	TN31	18:27	18:35		Y	967.1	51°29.67	11°49.04	51°29.67	11°49.07	Y	Y	Plastic bottle@ 18:32
7	TN32	18:39	18:45		Y	967.1	51°29.67	11°49.04	51°29.67	11°49.05	Y	Y	Plastic bottle @ 18:40; current moving @ 18:43

CE25006 Cruise Report: ROV Monitoring Survey

7	TN33	18:49	18:54	Kipro changed	Y	963.7	51°29.68	11°49.05	MISSING	MISSING	Y	Y	Plastic bottle @ 18:51
7	TN34	19:00	19:08		Y	963.7	51°29.68	11°49.05	51°29.68	11°49.05	Y	Y	
7	TN35	19:13	19:17		Y	963.7	51°29.68	11°49.05	51°29.68	11°49.05	Y	Y	Big fish @ 19:14
7	TN36	19:38	19:48		Y	968.1	51°29.63	11°49.02	51°29.63	11°49.02	Y	Y	Running lines E->W
7	TN37	19:54	20:05		Y	968.2	51°29.63	11°49.02	51°29.63	11°49.02	Y	Y	
7	TN38	20:08	20:18		Y	965.1	51°29.63	11°49.02	51°29.63	11°49.02	Y	Y	
7	TN39	20:23	20:31		Y	963.7	51°29.63	11°49.02	51°29.63	11°49.02	Y	Y	
7	TN40	20:35	20:45		Y	965.9	51°29.63	11°49.02	51°29.63	11°49.02	Y	Y	
7	TN41	20:50	20:57		Y	963.7	51°29.64	11°49.02	51°29.64	11°49.02	Y	Y	
7	TN42	21:02	21:09	Kipro changed	Y	963.7	51°29.64	11°49.02	51°29.64	11°49.02	Y	Y	
7	TN43	21:12	21:19		Y	963.7	51°29.64	11°49.02	51°29.64	11°49.02	Y	Y	
7	TN44	21:23	21:30		Y	963.7	51°29.64	11°49.02	51°29.64	11°49.02	Y	Y	
7	BS45	21:33	21:39		Y	963.7	51°29.64	11°49.02	51°29.64	11°49.02	Y	Y	
7	BS46	21:42	21:47		Y	963.7	51°29.64	11°49.02	51°29.64	11°49.02	Y	Y	
7	BS47	21:51	21:57		Y	963.7	51°29.64	11°49.02	51°29.64	11°49.02	Y	Y	
7	BS48	22:00	22:09		Y	963.7	51°29.64	11°49.02	51°29.64	11°49.02	Y	Y	
7	BS50	22:12	22:18		Y	963.7	51°29.64	11°49.02	51°29.64	11°49.02	Y	Y	additions to quincy map - paused briefly after this line
7	BS51	22:25	22:30		Y	963.7	51°29.64	11°49.03	51°29.64	11°49.03	Y	Y	
7	BS52	22:33	22:43		Y	963.7	51°29.64	11°49.03	51°29.64	11°49.03	Y	Y	
7	BS53	22:52	23:02		Y	963.7	51°29.64	11°49.03	51°29.64	11°49.03	Y	Y	
7	BS54	23:03	22:12	change before line	Y	963.7	51°29.64	11°49.03	51°29.64	11°49.03	Y	Y	started line north to south
7	BS55	23:14	23:28		Y	963.7	51°29.64	11°49.03	51°29.64	11°49.03	Y	Y	
7	BS56	23:34	23:49		Y	963.7	51°29.64	11°49.03	51°29.64	11°49.03	Y	Y	redo line BS54 S -> N; 23:45 adjusting line bearing
7	BS57	23:58	00:11		Y	963.6	51°29.64	11°49.03	51°29.64	11°49.03	Y	Y	
7	BS58	00:20	00:32		Y	963.6	51°29.64	11°49.03	51°29.6422	11°49.0273	Y	Y	Ship position has frozen - resorted to sonardyne ranger for EOL position
7	BS59	00:40	00:50		Y	964.2	51°29.6426	11°49.0359	51°29.6425	11°49.0367	Y	Y	
7	BS60	00:57	01:07	change after line	Y	963.3	51°29.6428	11°49.0445	51°29.6427	11°49.0457	Y	Y	
7	BS61	01:14	01:28		Y	964.2	51°29.6430	11°49.0468	51°29.6430	11°49.0462	Y	Y	
7	BS62	01:33	01:47		Y	963.8	51°29.6429	11°49.0456	51°29.6429	11°49.0456	Y	Y	
7	BS63	01:53	02:04		Y	963.7	51°29.64	11°49.0450	51°29.6427	11°49.0450	Y	Y	
7	TRANSI	02:07	02:49		Y	960.3	51°29.68	11°49.04	51°29.68	11°49.16	Y	Y	Line from E mound to W mound - crosses S side PIDD @ 02:26; new anemone @ 02:28
7	TN1	03:08	03:17	Kipro change	Y	961.4	51°29.60	11°49.18	51°29.68	11°49.14	Y	Y	New mound (W PIDD) Not on mound
7	TN2	03:29	03:34		Y	959.6	51°29.68	11°49.18	51°29.68	11°49.18	Y	Y	Center-ish line #40 on QUINSY GRID - covers N to S down middle of mound
7	TN3	03:38	03:45		Y	961.4	51°29.68	11°49.18	51°29.68	11°49.18	Y	Y	~2m left of TN2
7	TN4	03:51	03:59		Y	960.2	51°29.68	11°49.18	51°29.68	11°49.18	Y	Y	
7	TN5	04:05	04:13		Y	962.4	51°29.68	11°49.18	51°29.68	11°49.18	Y	Y	
7	NA	04:13	NA		Y	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Y	Y	Hoovering before recovering - South of small mound; 04:21 lifejacket. ROV on deck at 5:11

ROV Dive 3

ROV Dive4

ROV Dive5

ROV Dive6

ROV Dive7

Sediment Sampling log sheet, tracklines and images

Sediment Samples Log		DDM	DDM			
Station #	Event #	SAMPLE No	Lat	Long	Time (UTC)	Depth (m) Notes
7	3	1	51°36.33244	8°9.90753	08:16	80.4 Attempt 1 not succesful
7	3	1	51°36.32694	8°9.90358	08:25	80.6
7	4	2	51°36.3811	8°9.8717	08:45	80 Silty sand , some clay paletts, no smell
7	5	3	51°36.28615	8°10.0106	09:08	81
8	4	1	51°30.02621	8°47.53285	07:20	81.5 Muddy sand, no smell
8	5	2	51°30.03863	8°47.59299	07:29	82 Attempt 1 not succesful
8	5	2	51°30.03885	8°47.59422	07:35	80.6 Sand mud, no smell
8	6	3	51°29.95412	8°47.66010	07:52	81.1 Sand mud
9	3	NA	51°23.74	09°15.38	01:47	62.9 Attempt 1 not succesful
9	3	NA	51°23.74	09°15.37	01:52	62.8 Attempt 2 not succesful
9	3	NA	51°23.74894	09°15.38592	02:01	66.9 Attempt 3 not succesful
9	3	NA	51°23.74262	09°15.34091	02:15	69.8 Attempt 1 not succesful
9	3	NA	51°23.72951	09°15.35019	02:27	66.8 Attempt 2 not succesful
9	3	NA	51°23.75873	09°15.28201	02:46	69.9 Attempt 1 not succesful

Sediment Samples

CTD and SVP log sheet

CTD/SVP log				DDM	DDM			
Station #	Event	CTD #	SVP FILE NAME	Lat	Long	Time	Depth	Notes
2	1	1	02_01_SVPL_26_04_2025	51°23.14	09°17.39	03:42	66.2	Separate files for up and downcast
4	1	1		51°29.78	08°48.64	07:35	73.4	CTD on upcast started half way up
6	1	1		51°36.25	08°12.37	12:14	74.9	
8	1	1		51°30.10	08°47.43	11:46	72.6	
9	1	1		51°23.65	09°15.51	09:52	60.3	SVPs not used. Noted CTD is outputting the same value for SV

Geophysical and Hydrographic Log sheet

Log for Multibeam, SSS, Mag			Tick (x) for the type of equipment used							DDM	DDM	DDM	DDM		
Station #	Event #	Line #	EM302/EM2040	SideScan Sonar	Magnetometer	Start Time (UTC)	End Time (UTC)	Date	Start Latitude (DD)	Start Longitude (DD)	End Latitude (DD)	End Longitude (DD)	WCD? Y/N	note (302/2040)	
1	1	1	EM2040			17:02	11:25	Y	53°11.520	09°39.54	53°10.80	09°48.13	N	Test	
1	1	2	EM2040	X	X	12:15	12:34	25_04	53°06.57	09°56.75	53°05.47	09°57.43	N	Test (SSS, Mag, MBES)	
3	1	1	EM2040	X	X	04:15	04:31	26_04	52°23.51	09°15.74	051°24.22	09°14.57	N	USBL Dropping out a lot	
3	1	2	EM2040			04:40	05:03	26_04	51°24.38	09°14.45	51°23.27	09°16.27	N	Line not activated so	
3	1	2	EM2040	X	X	04:42	05:03	26_04	51°24.28	09°14.63	51°23.27	09°16.29	N	SSS Started later	
3	1	3	EM2040	X	X	05:19	05:42	26_04	51°23.24	09°16.19	51°24.26	09°14.41	Y	redo of 03-01	
5	1	1	EM2040	X	X	08:11	08:30	26_04	51°29.95	08°48.10	51°30.06	08°46.83	N		
5	1	2	EM2040	X	X	08:46	09:06	26_04	51°30.54	08°47.08	51°29.49	08°48.32	N	Slight offset due to changing survey plan	
5	1	3	EM2040	X	X	09:26	09:46	26_04	51°29.51	08°54.07	51°30.61	08°46.76	Y	WCL just at the wreck	
7	1	1	EM2040	X	X	13:08	13:30	26_04	51°36.21	08°11.18	51°36.39	08°08.80	Y	WCL just at the wreck	
7	1	2	EM2040	X	X	13:35	14:12	26_04	51°36.46	08°08.71	51°36.28	08°11.05	N		
7	1	3	EM2040	X	X	14:33	14:59	26_04	51°36.27	08°11.12	51°36.44	08°08.96	Y	WCL just at the wreck	
8	2	1	EM2040			12:08	12:11	27_04	51°30.051	08°47.625	51°29.94	08°47.37	N	Patch test 4 kn	
8	2	2	EM2040			12:24	12:27	27_04	51°30.06	08°47.32	51°30.18	08°47.62	N	Patch test 4 kn	
8	2	3	EM2040			12:38	12:42	27_04	51°38.08	08°47.68	51°29.92	08°47.30	Y	Patch test 4 kn	
8	2	4	EM2040			12:54	12:58	27_04	51°29.96	08°47.41	51°30.11	08°47.78	N	Patch test 4 kn	
8	2	5	EM2040			13:13	13:15	27_04	51°30.07	08°47.66	51°29.90	08°47.25	N	Patch test 8 kn	
10	1	1	EM2040	X	X	10:43	14:39	29_04	51°27.57	11°13.24	051°28.04	011°33.89	N	Transit Geophys Survey - changed from USBL to COG Celtic Explorer in Quinsy	

Data Backup Log sheet

Attribute	Data Type						Folder location	Folder size	Notes
	Date	HD1	HD2	MI HD	By				
0	ROV								
1	HD Video	01/05/2025	x	x	x	LO	SEMI-WARE_CE25006\01_Raw_Data\ROV_video\	2.84T	ROV_video folders also copied to the Marine Institute HD as per MI's request
2	Digitstills	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not acquired
3	Composite video (end of every dive)	01/05/2025	x	x	x	LO	SEMI-WARE_CE25006\01_Raw_Data\ROV_video\Composite\	57.7	Downward facing composite camera
4	ROV CTD	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Not acquired
5	INS	01/05/2025	x	x		LO	SEMI-WARE_CE25006\01_Raw_Data\ROV_video\INS\	423MB	Not acquired for the coral mounds due to technical issues with the ROV positioning
6	MBES								
7	Raw EM2040 water column data (*.wcd)	01/05/2025	x	x	NA	LO	SEMI-WARE_CE25006\01_Raw_Data\Multibeam\EM2040\	6.80Gb	Collected near the wrecks
8	Raw EM2040 MBES line files (*.all)	01/05/2025	x	x	NA	LO	SEMI-WARE_CE25006\01_Raw_Data\Multibeam\EM2040\	6.80Gb	Collected at shipwreck sites and at transit to coral mounds (tow test)
9	SVP's (converted from the CTD)	01/05/2025	x	x	NA	LO	SEMI-WARE_CE25006\01_Raw_Data\SVP\	7.3KB	Converted from CTD (Rosette)
10	Magnetometry				NA	LO			
11	Qinsy folder	01/05/2025	x	x	NA	LO	SEMI-WARE_CE25006\01_Raw_Data\Quinsy\UCC_Shipwrecks_2025	1.09Gb	
	Mag files (.txt)	01/05/2025	x	x	NA	LO	SEMI-WARE_CE25006\01_Raw_Data\Magnetometer\	13.4MB	
12	Side Scan Sonar				NA	LO			
13	EdgeTech .jsf files	01/05/2025	x	x	NA	LO	SEMI-WARE_CE25006\01_Raw_Data\Sidescan\	2.97GB	
14	Positioning								
15	USBL Sonardyne Ranger2 and GGA files	01/05/2025	x	x	NA	LO	SEMI-WARE_CE25006\01_Raw_Data\USBL\	4.66GB	Collected from the technician, original files names as per technician
16	CTD	01/05/2025	x	x	NA	LO	SEMI-WARE_CE25006\01_Raw_Data\CTD\	5.13	Sound velocity values on CTD were recorded as the same value leading to issue with SVP.
17	Misc.	01/05/2025			NA	LO			
18	Cruise photos	01/05/2025			NA	LO			
19	Digital Log sheets	01/05/2025	x	x	NA	LO	SEMI-WARE_CE25006\03_Logs\		
20	Cruise GIS files	01/05/2025	x	x	NA	LO			
21	Cruise report	01/05/2025			NA	LO			

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